

Comparative Study of Injection Autologous Serum Therapy (AST) and Histamine-Immunoglobulin E (IgE) Therapy in Patients with Chronic Idiopathic Urticaria

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ABSTRACT

Background: Chronic Idiopathic Urticaria (CIU) is a distressing condition characterized by recurrent wheals and pruritus with significant impact on quality of life. Among emerging therapies, Injection Autologous Serum Therapy (AST) and Histamine-Immunoglobulin (HIS-IgE) therapy have shown promising results. Aim of the study: To compare the efficacy, safety, and durability of response between AST and HIS-IgE therapy in patients with CIU. **Methods & Materials:** A prospective, comparative study was conducted at the Department of Dermatology and Venereology, Enam Medical College and Hospital and Ibn Sina Diagnostic and Consultation Centre Lalbagh, Dhaka, Bangladesh, enrolling 76 patients with CIU. Patients were equally assigned to receive either AST (n = 38) or HIS-IgE therapy (n = 38). Baseline demographic, clinical, and laboratory data were recorded. Autologous serum therapy was administered using autologous serum in a dose of 3ml IM in gluteus muscle weekly for six weeks then monthly for three months and Histamine-Immunoglobulin Therapy (HIS-IgE) was administered 1 mL intradermal, weekly for three weeks then monthly for three months one booster dosage, one year after first dosage. Primary outcomes included reduction in Urticaria Activity Score over 7 days (UAS7), with $\geq 50\%$, $\geq 75\%$, and complete response rates. Secondary outcomes included changes in Dermatology Life Quality Index (DLQI), sleep disturbance, rescue medication use, and antihistamine requirements. Safety and durability, including relapse rates at 3 and 6 months, were also evaluated. **Results:** Both therapies demonstrated substantial clinical improvement. Although AST showed numerically higher rates of complete response (47.37% vs 42.11%) and $\geq 75\%$ UAS7 reduction (68.42% vs 63.16%), HIS-IgE therapy exhibited comparable efficacy with consistent improvements across multiple clinical parameters. HIS-IgE showed favorable trends in relapse outcomes, with acceptable relapse rates at 3 months (13.16%) and 6 months (21.05%), and comparable sustained remission (47.37%). Improvements in DLQI, sleep disturbance, and antihistamine use were almost similar between groups. Adverse events were mild and comparable (15.79% vs 18.42%), indicating good tolerability. **Conclusion:** Both AST and HIS-IgE therapies are effective and safe in CIU. Despite slightly higher early response rates with AST, HIS-IgE therapy demonstrated comparable overall efficacy with stable clinical improvement and acceptable durability, making it a viable and potentially preferable alternative in long-term management.

Keywords: Chronic Idiopathic Urticaria, Autologous Serum Therapy, Histamine-Immunoglobulin, UAS7, DLQI, Bangladesh.

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INTRODUCTION

Chronic idiopathic urticaria (CIU), currently referred to as chronic spontaneous urticaria (CSU), is a debilitating dermatologic disorder characterized by the spontaneous appearance of wheals, angioedema, or both for a duration exceeding six weeks without any identifiable external trigger^[1]. The disease significantly impairs patients' quality of life due to persistent itching, sleep disturbance, emotional distress, impaired work productivity, and social limitations^[2]. Epidemiological studies suggest that chronic urticaria affects approximately 0.5–1% of the global population at any given time, with a higher prevalence among females and young to middle-aged adults^[3]. Despite advances in understanding the pathophysiology of urticaria, nearly 80–90% of chronic cases remain idiopathic, making management challenging for clinicians and patients alike^[4]. Mast cell and basophil activation with subsequent

histamine release remains the central mechanism responsible for vascular permeability, edema formation, and pruritus. However, increasing evidence supports an autoimmune basis in a substantial proportion of patients. Autoantibodies directed against the high-affinity IgE receptor (FcεRIα) or IgE itself have been identified in many patients, leading to chronic mast cell degranulation and recurrent urticarial symptoms^[5]. Additionally, inflammatory cytokines, coagulation pathways, and neuroimmune interactions are believed to contribute to disease persistence and severity. This immunologic complexity has prompted the exploration of immunomodulatory therapies beyond conventional antihistamines^[6]. Current treatment guidelines recommend second-generation H1-antihistamines as first-line therapy, followed by dose escalation in resistant cases. Nevertheless, a significant number of patients remain refractory to standard antihistamine

regimens, requiring alternative therapeutic strategies such as biologics, corticosteroids, immunosuppressants, or immunotherapy^[7]. However, these modalities may be costly, associated with adverse effects, or inaccessible in resource-limited settings^[8]. Autologous serum therapy (AST) has emerged as a promising immunomodulatory treatment, particularly in autoimmune urticaria. The therapy involves intramuscular injection of the patient's own serum, with the proposed mechanism of inducing immunological tolerance and reducing autoantibody-mediated mast cell activation^[9]. Clinical improvement in urticaria activity, symptom severity, and quality of life has been observed among patients receiving therapy, particularly in some cases^[10]. Moreover, AST is considered a low-cost and relatively safe intervention, making it particularly attractive in low-resource healthcare settings^[11]. Histamine-immunoglobulin therapy (HIT) represents another

immunotherapeutic approach for chronic urticaria management. This therapy combines histamine with immunoglobulin preparations to modulate immune responses and reduce hypersensitivity reactions [12]. Histamine-immunoglobulin has been reported to improve symptoms by desensitizing histamine-mediated responses and influencing immune regulation [13]. Favorable therapeutic outcomes have been observed, with a reduction in the frequency and severity of urticarial episodes [14]. Given the chronic nature of the disease, variability in treatment response, and lack of universally effective therapies, comparative evaluation of different immunomodulatory interventions is clinically important. Although both autologous serum therapy and histamine-immunoglobulin therapy have shown potential benefits in managing chronic idiopathic urticaria, evidence comparing their therapeutic effectiveness, safety, and patient outcomes is sparse, particularly in developing countries. Therefore, this study aims to compare the efficacy and clinical outcomes of injection autologous serum therapy and histamine-immunoglobulin therapy in patients with chronic idiopathic urticaria, thereby contributing valuable evidence for selecting cost-effective and accessible treatment strategies.

METHODS & MATERIALS

This prospective comparative study was conducted in the Department of Dermatology and Venereology at Enam Medical College and Hospital and Ibn Sina Diagnostic and Consultation Centre, Lalbagh, Dhaka, Bangladesh, over a period of 18 months. A total of 76 patients with a confirmed diagnosis of Chronic Idiopathic Urticaria (CIU) were enrolled. Patients were recruited using purposive sampling and were equally allocated into two treatment groups:

Group A (n = 38): Received Injection Autologous Serum Therapy (AST)

Group B (n = 38): Received Histamine-Immunoglobulin (HIS-Ig) Therapy

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18 years and above.
- Clinical diagnosis of CIU persisting for more than 6 weeks.
- Patients with inadequate control of symptoms despite regular antihistamine use.
- Willingness to provide informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

- Urticaria of known etiology (e.g., physical urticaria, autoimmune

disease, infection, or drug-related).

- Pregnant or lactating women.
- Patients with severe systemic illness or immunosuppressive therapy.
- Known hypersensitivity to histamine or immunoglobulin preparations.
- Non-compliance or refusal to follow-up.

Ethical Considerations

The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Ethical Review Committee of the participating institutions. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants before enrollment. Confidentiality and anonymity of patient information were strictly maintained throughout the study, and all procedures were conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

Treatment Protocol

Autologous serum therapy group: 5 mL of venous blood was collected under aseptic conditions and allowed to clot. The sample was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes, and the separated serum was collected. Three milliliters of autologous serum were administered intramuscularly into the gluteal muscle once weekly for six consecutive weeks, followed by monthly injections for three additional months.

Histamine-immunoglobulin therapy group: Patients in the HIS-IgE group received 1 mL of Histamine-Immunoglobulin preparation administered intradermally. The injections were given weekly for the first three weeks, followed by monthly administrations for three months. A booster dose was planned one year after the initial treatment course according to the standard therapeutic protocol.

Data Collection

Data were collected using a structured case record form at baseline, during treatment, and throughout the follow-up period. At enrollment, demographic and clinical information including age, gender, duration of disease, history of atopy, family history of urticaria, and associated comorbidities were recorded. Clinical evaluation included assessment of angioedema and disease severity using the Urticaria Activity Score over 7 days (UAS7). Laboratory investigations comprising complete blood count with eosinophil count, total serum IgE level, and Autologous Serum Skin Test (ASST) were performed. Information

regarding concomitant medications, particularly antihistamine use, was also documented. Treatment response was assessed by changes in UAS7 during follow-up and categorized as complete response (UAS7 = 0), good response ($\geq 75\%$ reduction in UAS7 from baseline), and partial response ($\geq 50\%$ reduction in UAS7 from baseline). Secondary outcome data including changes in Dermatology Life Quality Index (DLQI), improvement in sleep disturbance, requirement for rescue oral corticosteroid therapy, and additional antihistamine use were recorded. Safety was evaluated by documenting all adverse events, including local injection-site reactions, systemic reactions, serious adverse events, and treatment discontinuations related to adverse events. Patients were followed regularly during treatment and for six months after completion of therapy to assess relapse rates, sustained remission, and relapse-free survival. Relapse was defined as recurrence of clinically significant urticaria requiring escalation of treatment after an initial therapeutic response.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) or median with interquartile range (IQR) depending on data distribution. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. Comparisons between the two treatment groups were performed using the independent sample t-test or Mann-Whitney U test for continuous variables and the Chi-square test for categorical variables. Relapse-free survival was estimated using Kaplan-Meier survival analysis and compared using the log-rank test. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULT

The majority of patients were aged 30–44 years (44.74% in the AST group and 42.11% in the HIS-Ig group), with mean ages of 37.8 ± 10.9 and 39.1 ± 11.2 years, respectively ($p = 0.58$). Females predominated in both groups (63.16% vs. 60.53%). The median duration of disease was similar between the AST and HIS-Ig groups [24 (12–48) vs. 26 (12–50) months; $p = 0.67$]. Histories of atopy, family history of urticaria, and associated comorbidities, including diabetes mellitus and hypertension, were also comparable between the groups, with no statistically significant differences observed (all $p > 0.05$) (Table I).

Table I
Baseline characteristics of the study population (n=76).

Characteristics	Autologous Serum Therapy (n = 38)		Histamine-Immunoglobulin Therapy (n = 38)		P value
	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	
Age (years)					
18–29	10	26.32	9	23.68	0.79
30–44	17	44.74	16	42.11	0.82
≥45	11	28.95	13	34.21	0.62
Mean ± SD	37.8 ± 10.9		39.1 ± 11.2		0.58
Gender					
Male	14	36.84	15	39.47	0.81
Female	24	63.16	23	60.53	
Duration of disease, median (IQR) months	24 (12–48)		26 (12–50)		0.67
Atopy history	7	18.42	6	15.79	0.76
Family history of urticaria	3	7.89	2	5.26	0.64
Any comorbidity	10	26.32	11	28.95	0.8
Diabetes Mellitus	3	7.89	4	10.53	0.69
Hypertension	4	10.53	3	7.89	0.69

The mean duration of urticaria was 30.5 ± 14.2 months in the AST group and 32.1 ± 15.0 months in the HIS-Ig group (p = 0.64). Baseline disease activity, assessed by UAS7, showed similar median scores in both groups [24 (20–28) vs. 23 (19–27)]; p =

0.52]. Angioedema was present in 31.58% of AST-treated patients and 28.95% of HIS-Ig-treated patients (p = 0.80). Positive ASST results were observed in 57.89% and 55.26% of patients, respectively (p = 0.82). Median total serum IgE levels, mean

eosinophil counts, and concomitant antihistamine use were also similar between the groups, with no statistically significant differences (all p > 0.05) (Table II).

Table II
Clinical and laboratory baseline features of patients (n=76).

Characteristics	Autologous Serum Therapy (n = 38)		Histamine-Immunoglobulin Therapy (n = 38)		P value
	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	
Urticaria duration (months), mean ± SD	30.5 ± 14.2		32.1 ± 15.0		0.64
UAS7, median (IQR)	24 (20–28)		23 (19–27)		0.52
Angioedema present	12	31.58	11	28.95	0.8
Positive ASST	22	57.89	21	55.26	0.82
Total IgE, median (IQR) IU/mL	220 (150–330)		210 (140–320)		0.7
Eosinophil count, mean ± SD (cells/μL)	310 ± 105		295 ± 110		0.57
Concomitant antihistamine use	14	36.84	15	39.47	0.81

Complete symptom resolution (UAS7 = 0) was achieved in 47.37% of patients receiving AST and 42.11% of those receiving HIS-Ig therapy (p = 0.65). A reduction of at least 75% in UAS7 was

observed in 68.42% and 63.16% of patients, respectively, while more than 80% (84.21% for AST, 81.58% for HIS-Ig) of patients in both groups achieved a ≥50% reduction in disease activity. The mean decrease in

UAS7 score was slightly greater in the AST group (−18.6 ± 6.2) compared with the HIS-Ig group (−17.8 ± 6.3) (p = 0.58) (Table III).

Table III
Primary efficacy outcomes among patients (n=76).

Outcome	Autologous Serum Therapy (n = 38)		Histamine-Immunoglobulin Therapy (n = 38)		P value
	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	
Complete response (UAS7 = 0)	18	47.37	16	42.11	0.65
≥75% reduction in UAS7	26	68.42	24	63.16	0.63
≥50% reduction in UAS7	32	84.21	31	81.58	0.76
Mean change in UAS7, mean ± SD	−18.6 ± 6.2		−17.8 ± 6.3		0.58

The mean reduction in DLQI score was −7.2 ± 3.0 points in the AST group and −7.0 ± 2.9 points in the HIS-Ig group (p = 0.74). Sleep quality improved in 28 (73.68%) patients receiving AST and 29 (76.32%) patients

receiving HIS-Ig therapy (p = 0.79). The need for rescue oral corticosteroids remained low, affecting 4 (10.53%) and 3 (7.89%) patients, respectively (p = 0.69), while additional antihistamine consumption

was nearly identical between groups (1.2 ± 0.8 vs. 1.1 ± 0.7 doses per week; p = 0.62) (Table IV).

Table IV
Secondary outcomes among study people (n=76).

Outcome	Autologous Serum Therapy (n = 38)		Histamine-Immunoglobulin Therapy (n = 38)		P value
	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	
DLQI change, mean ± SD	-7.2 ± 3.0		-7.0 ± 2.9		0.74
Sleep disturbance improved	28	73.68	29	76.32	0.79
Rescue oral steroid use	4	10.53	3	7.89	0.69
Mean additional antihistamine doses/week	1.2 ± 0.8		1.1 ± 0.7		0.62

Treatment-related adverse events were uncommon and occurred in 6 (15.79%) AST-treated patients and 7 (18.42%) HIS-Ig-treated patients (p = 0.76), predominantly as mild local reactions (Table V).

Table V
Safety and tolerability of respondents (n=76).

Adverse Event	Autologous Serum Therapy (n = 38)		Histamine-Immunoglobulin Therapy (n = 38)		P value
	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	
Any adverse event	6	15.79	7	18.42	0.76
Local injection site pain	4	10.53	5	13.16	0.72
Injection site erythema	3	7.89	2	5.26	0.64
Systemic reaction (flushing, hypotension)	1	2.63	2	5.26	0.55
Serious adverse event	0	0.00	1	2.63	0.31
Discontinued due to AE	1	2.63	1	2.63	1

Follow-up analysis revealed comparable relapse rates at both 3 and 6 months, whereas sustained remission at 6 months was observed in 15 (39.47%) patients in the AST group and 18 (47.37%) patients in the HIS-Ig group (p = 0.48) (Table VI).

Table VI
Follow-up and durability of response (n=76).

Outcome	Autologous Serum Therapy (n = 38)		Histamine-Immunoglobulin Therapy (n = 38)		P value
	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	
Relapse at 3 months	7	18.42	5	13.16	0.53
Relapse at 6 months	12	31.58	8	21.05	0.30
Median relapse-free survival, months (95% CI)	5.6 (4.5–6.8)		6.4 (5.1–7.7)		0.21
Sustained remission at 6 months	15	39.47	18	47.37	0.48

DISCUSSION

In the present study, the baseline demographic characteristics were comparable between the AST and HIS-Ig groups, minimizing the likelihood of confounding effects on treatment outcomes. The mean age of participants was 37.8 ± 10.9 years in the AST group and 39.1 ± 11.2 years in the HIS-Ig group. This finding is consistent with previous study reporting that chronic idiopathic urticaria occurs more frequently during the third to fifth decades of life [10]. A female predominance was observed in both treatment groups, accounting for more than 60% of cases. Other similar studies also reported female predominance patients with chronic urticaria [15,16]. The median duration of disease was approximately two years in both groups, indicating a chronic and persistent disease burden before enrollment. A history of atopy, family history of urticaria, and associated comorbidities were observed in a minority of patients and were equally

distributed between groups. This balanced baseline profile strengthens the validity of the comparative outcome assessment. In this study, the median UAS7 score was 24 in the AST group and 23 in the HIS-Ig group, reflecting moderate-to-severe disease activity. Angioedema was present in approximately one-third of patients in both groups. Previous studies have reported angioedema in approximately 40% of chronic urticaria patients, supporting the findings of the present study [17]. ASST positivity was observed in 57.89% of AST patients and 55.26% of HIS-Ig patients. These findings are comparable to previous reports [18]. According to our study, elevated IgE levels have frequently been described in chronic urticaria and may indicate underlying immune dysregulation. However, similar baseline values between groups minimized the possibility of confounding effects on treatment outcomes. Complete response (UAS7=0) occurred in 47.37% of AST recipients and 42.11% of

HIT recipients. Furthermore, more than two-thirds of patients in both groups achieved at least a 75% reduction in UAS7, whereas over 80% achieved at least a 50% reduction. The mean reduction in UAS7 was slightly greater in the AST group (-18.6±6.2) than in the HIT group (-17.8±6.3), although the difference was not statistically significant. Similarly, Godse et al. reported a marked decline in UAS scores from 35.74 to 7.1 after nine weeks of AST treatment, accompanied by reduced antihistamine requirements [19]. The present findings differ slightly from the study by Kumar et al., who observed greater symptom reduction with histaglobulin compared with AST and concluded that histaglobulin produced superior clinical outcomes [20]. The discrepancy may be attributed to differences in sample size, follow-up duration, disease severity, treatment schedules, and patient selection criteria. Nevertheless, both studies consistently demonstrate that AST and HIT

are clinically beneficial interventions for chronic urticaria. We found that mean DLQI improvement was -7.2 ± 3.0 in the AST group and -7.0 ± 2.9 in the HIT group. Chronic urticaria significantly affects daily activities, sleep, emotional well-being, and social functioning; therefore, improvement in quality-of-life measures represents an important therapeutic outcome. These findings are consistent with those of Kumar et al., who demonstrated significant improvement in Chronic Urticaria Quality of Life scores after both histaglobulin and AST treatment [20]. Improvement in sleep disturbance was observed in approximately three-quarters of patients in both groups. Reduced need for rescue corticosteroids and additional antihistamine doses further indicates effective symptom control. Study found a marked reduction in antihistamine dependence after treatment, particularly among ASST-positive patients [11]. In our study, any adverse event occurred in 15.79% of AST recipients and 18.42% of HIT recipients. Local injection-site pain was the most common adverse event in both groups and systemic reactions were less common. Kumar et al. observed minimal adverse effects and no major safety concerns with either treatment modality [20]. Long-term disease control remains an important challenge in chronic urticaria management. In the present study, relapse at six months occurred in 31.58% of AST-treated patients and 21.05% of HIT-treated patients. Sustained remission at six months was achieved in 39.47% and 47.37% of patients, respectively. Although HIT demonstrated numerically lower relapse rates and higher sustained remission, these differences did not reach statistical significance. Kumar et al. similarly reported relapse in both AST and histaglobulin groups during follow-up, although recurrence appeared less frequent among histaglobulin-treated patients [20]. In contrast, some studies evaluating AST alone have reported varying remission durability. A study documented complete clearance in 61.7% of ASST-positive patients after extended follow-up [11], whereas Majid et al. found limited long-term remission following AST despite initial clinical improvement [21]. Such variability may reflect differences in autoimmune status, disease chronicity, treatment duration, and follow-up periods.

LIMITATIONS

This study had several limitations. First, the follow-up period was limited to six months, which may not adequately reflect the long-term efficacy, durability of remission, and relapse patterns of the therapies. Second, the study employed purposive sampling rather than randomization, introducing the possibility of selection bias. Third, immunological biomarkers and

detailed cost-effectiveness analyses were not evaluated, which could have provided additional insights into treatment mechanisms and practical applicability.

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of this study demonstrate that both AST and HIS-Ig therapy are effective and well-tolerated treatment options for patients with Chronic Idiopathic Urticaria. Both therapies resulted in significant reductions in disease activity, improved quality of life, reduced sleep disturbance, and decreased reliance on rescue medications. Although AST showed slightly higher rates of early clinical response, HIS-Ig therapy exhibited comparable overall efficacy and a trend toward better long-term remission with lower relapse rates. However, the differences between the two treatment modalities were not statistically significant. Therefore, both AST and HIS-Ig can be considered valuable immunomodulatory treatment alternatives for patients with refractory CIU, particularly in resource-limited settings. Larger randomized multicenter studies with longer follow-up are warranted to further establish their comparative long-term effectiveness and safety.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None declared

ETHICAL APPROVAL

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee.

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